

THE SERVICE SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN: CURRENT STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS

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Abstract: *This article describes the enhancement of productivity in the service sector, as well as its institutional arrangements*

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In the conditions of development of market relations, it is important to properly shape the sphere of service from the organizational and economic point of view. If the development of this industry is organizational optimal and flexible in relation to the services market conjuncture, then the quality and efficiency of service delivery will be so high. The proper organization of labor activities in the service sector will lead to the elimination of a number of social and economic problems at the level of the national economy. For example, the provision of employment of the population on the basis of the development of the industry, the increase in the business activity of the servants, the operative Organization of the services provided, etc., will lead to the improvement in the level and quality of life of the population of the country, which will ultimately lead to an increase in the number

In the service sector, the complexity and variety of components of the production and service process, the possibility of independent selection, calculation, design and coordination of their implementation activities make significant changes to the content of the work.

In the current conditions, it is necessary not only to establish interaction of workers ' activities with the components of labor, but also to formulate labor relations between the "human-technical" participants of the interaction activities, to solve such problems as increasing the efficiency of live labor.

In our opinion, the organizational structure of the service sector of foreign countries through the research of the organizational structure of the

services market, we can classify the organizational structure of the services market in our country as follows:

- according to the rules of practice (intermediary financial, information-technological, legal, marketing);
- by the form of property (private, cooperative (community), public, Foreign);
- on the scale of services provided (international, national, regional, local);
- by Types and directions of services provided: Business Services (Financial, Insurance, Credit Services), Distribution Services (trade, catering), Social Services (Education, Health, Physical Culture, legal services).

Many foreign Economist scientists propose to classify the structural structure of the service sector from the point of view of its network signs and development. In our opinion, it is desirable to classify this area from an organizational and economic point of view.

In this case, it is necessary to distinguish the following separately:

- information and commercial infrastructure (marketing centers, advertising agencies, information collection and processing centers, etc.the z.);
- economic and legal infrastructure (courts, legal advisory centers, advisory and notary offices, etc.)z);
- financial and credit infrastructure (commercial banks, credit, insurance and guarantee organizations);
- trade, intermediary infrastructure (fairs, birja, commercial houses, commercial centers).

The above-mentioned classifications are important in ensuring the efficiency of the service sector. However, reforms aimed at increasing the impact of services in the economic policy of our country require further development of these areas of services. For example, it has a positive impact on the realisation of commercial houses, organizations, fairs, food and non-food products as well as their productive activities as types of services. However, services as a special commodity require its providers to fulfill specific requirements.

It is known that at present, commercial banks rarely allocate loans to small and private entrepreneurs operating in the service sector. The reason for such a situation is the lack of the volume of financial operations in service enterprises, the inability to provide the necessary guarantees for the loan, as well as the issues of stability of these enterprises.

Another organizational dimension of increasing the effectiveness of the activities of service enterprises is the information system that serves the industry. This system covers, in our opinion, the following: advertising agencies, marketing service centers, permanent or migratory displays, media and electronic communication systems, etc. In our opinion, the further development of information supply in the service sector provides the population with the opportunity to fully satisfy their ability to pay for services, evaluate the dynamics of growth in this area, improve the quality and efficiency of services provided. To do this, it is necessary to establish a special service-marketing centers-to study the demand for services at the regional level. This organizational structure includes the following areas of activity:

- development of scientific and practical hands-on study of demand and supply for new types of services;
- preparation of reports, booklets, lectures for the provision of services on a regional scale for those who need services;
- conducting surveys, sociological research to determine the quality of service provided;
- participation in social events, fairs, exhibitions to solve problems in the field of services.

In summary, the factors that influence the change in employee status in the process of production or service delivery will depend on the reason and circumstances that are updated or changed in the impact of a process. The scientific-technical and technological progress of production or service delivery is an evidence-based reason for the change in employee status in labor processes. The organization of Labor and service processes in a way connected with technology-technology is also constantly changing.

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